

Intervention In A Free Living Male Royal Bengal Tiger (*Panthera Tigris Tigris*) For Treatment, Rehabilitation And Release In Natural Habitat

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Abstract:

An Injured 4-5 years old male adult tiger (*Panthera tigris tigris*) was rescued from Harda Forest Division, Madhya Pradesh, a central Indian Province. In clinical observation, tiger had four punctured wound on the forehead and one lacerated wound on left hind limb. The tiger was unable to lift the hind quarter, and also had fracture on the skull of forehead and hind limb. For advanced treatment the tiger was shifted to Van Vihar National Park, Bhopal where the extent of injury was evaluated, treated and released in its natural habitat. The tiger was anesthetized by xylazine & ketamine for assessing the healing status of the wounds and after treated for 45 days, the tiger was smoothly released in the natural habitat of tigers in Satpura Tiger Reserve.

Key Words: Royal Bengal Tiger (*Panthera tigris tigris*), Fracture, Wound, Suturing, Release.

Introduction:

India is home for 75% of the total world tiger population, with 77% residing in and around its 53 tiger reserves and other Protected Areas of country and remaining tigers inhabit

various forest patches in Territorial Forest Divisions within multi-use landscapes (1). The population count of Royal Bengal Tiger (*Panthera tigris tigris*) of India in 2023 is 3167 and the central Indian Landscapes is home for largest number of tigers in India. The Central Indian province, Madhya Pradesh (7 Tiger reserves and 3 proposed new tiger reserves) has highest population count (785 nos.) in India in its. The increase in the population count also invites higher incidences of man-tiger conflict situation, especially in the vicinity of buffer zones of PAs and forest areas of territorial division. The present report is a case of active intervention to rescue of a male tiger from man-tiger conflict situation from territorial forest division of Harda, Madhya Pradesh and its evaluation of injuries, treatment, release in the Satpura Tiger Reserve, Madhya Pradesh, India.

Case history, diagnosis and treatment:

An adult male tiger (*Panthera tigris tigris*) morphologically estimated approx. aged 4-5 years, having multiple wounds on the forehead over the frontal bone and left hind limb over the biceps femoris muscle was rescued from Rehatgaon range of Harda forest division (22.183609°N; 77.295225°E) (Fig 1) and brought to Van Vihar National Park, Bhopal. The tiger had relatively old injuries with necrotic tissues caused by sharp weapon and was within the reach to lick the wounds. The 150 kgs (Approximate) weigh tiger was chemically immobilized using ilium Xylazil 100 (@1.5 mg/kg body wt., Troy Animal Healthcare) and ketamine hydrochloride (@3mg/kg body wt., Troy Animal Healthcare) by i/m route delivered by projectile syringe. It took 7mins for the tiger to sit laterally. The tiger was unable to move and bear weight on the hindquarter. The vital parameters of the animal was monitored manually during the sedation period of 15 minutes. The tiger was translocated in a transportation cage to Van Vihar National Park Zoo for further treatment. The tiger was re-anesthetized in squeeze cage following 12 hrs of fasting and was radiographically examined (Allengers- OPEL15, Allengers Medi System) for fracture of skull and hindlimb in its dorso-lateral view and lateral view at mAS 20 & 16, Kv 70 & 60, respectively. The animal was given a course of antibiotics for 7days, vitamins and calcium supplementation for 15 days. Blood was collected (5ml) by venipuncture of caudal vein in a clot activator tube and vials containing EDTA (@2mg/ml) during the rescue and before the release of the tiger.

Result:

The anesthetic drugs using Xylazine-hydrochloride and Ketamine- hydrochloride produced desired anesthetic effect for 15 to 25 minutes for rescue and clinical investigation.

The tiger had four deep penetrating wounds on frontal region of the skull (Fig 2). The wound “a” and “d” were approximately 6-7 cm deep where frontal bone was palpable. Wound “b” and “c” were 4-5cm deep. A lacerated wound (15 cm X 3 cm approx.) was observed over the metatarsal region of the left hind limb. Upon radiographic examination of tiger, five fractures were recorded-3 fractures were seen in the frontal bone while two fractures in the metatarsal of the left hind limb (Fig. 3). Among the five fractures in the lacrimal bone, at the rim of eye orbit was transverse fracture while remaining four were hairline fractures. The open wounds on the skull were sutured absorbable surgical suture, (Vicryl plus, No.1, Ethicon) in simple continuous pattern and antiseptic dressing with Betadine ointment, Hydroheal AM hydrogel was done for all the wounds. Antibiotics (Ceftizoxime @ 2g bid for 5days), analgesics (Meloxicam, Integrated laboratories, @0.1mg/kg body weight for 3 days) and multivitamins (Vitamino multi, Agrovit, @4ml for 5 days) were administered intramuscularly. Calcium supplementation (Calcium carbonate @2g) was provided orally with the meat for 15 days. The hemato-biochemical parameters (IDEXX Procyte Dx and IDEXX catalyst One, IDEXX laboratories) of the Tiger during the rescue and after treatments were shown in Table 1.

Discussion:

Tiger occupancy has expanded to various territorial regions in Madhya Pradesh (1). Tiger is critically endangered species owing to habitat destruction, poaching, retaliatory killing population (2). Rehabilitation activities include treatment, care and release of such diseased/disabled wild animals to their natural wild habitat as well as reintroduction of extinct species in a region from another abundant territory (3).

In the present study, after 1 month of rescue and continuous treatment, significant improvements and healing were observed in all the wounds as well as at all fracture sites (Fig 4). Three out of four wounds in frontal region were seen to be completely dry and closed. One Septic wound in metatarsal region of left hind limb was seen to have pinkish granulation tissue with all cardinal sign of healing. An ideal wound dressing should be multifunctional by guaranteeing hemostasis, moisture balance, oxygen exchange, antibacterial action and by working as a skin regeneration enhancer for effective wound healing (4). The tiger was found to bearing weight on all the four limbs, was found to be active and start responding to different stimuli. The hemato-biochemical values in the rescued tiger post treatment were comparable to parameters in the previously studied tiger population (2,5).

Normally, a male cub separates from her mother at the age of 2 years to establish its own territory. In the process, the tigers travel long distances, such as transient tigers stray into villages, towns and even cities searching for suitable habitat having good prey base, water availability, cover to hide and mate to reproduce. It was during such time that the tiger may have come in contact with unaware villagers initially and the repercussions due to loss of livestock and injuries caused to human life. Accidental mauling or killing of humans by tigers is rare and usually occurs when angry mobs surround tigers that enter human settlements to take livestock (6). The area of the incident is in the apex position of a triangle between the middle of two tiger reserves namely Melghat Tiger Reserve and Satpura Tiger Reserve, though the distance from the latter is less (Fig.1). The injuries inflicted by sharp weapons by villagers to scare away the tiger caused the skin injuries in the forehead, hind limbs and fracture on the skull.

Conclusion:

The tiger (with intact claw & canine) was rescued and treated successfully for the period of 45 days. The tiger responded to applied treatment regimens and showed significant improvement. The extent of injuries may be fatal for a tiger if left untreated in wild condition. Keeping an eye on the improvements the extent of healing of the hairline fractures, it was decided to do a soft release of the tiger in Satpura Tiger Reserve. The need of the hour is to carry out such interventions outside the protected areas, in the corridor connectivity for most effective conservation of tigers as well as ensure resilience to keep the system functioning.

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Fig.1: Locations of Harda territorial forest division in the the map of India

Fig.2: Injures on forehead and left hind limb of the tiger

Table 1: Comparative Hemato-biochemical parameters of the tiger.

	During the rescue	After completion of the treatment	Reference values (Range ± SE)
Hematological parameters			
Haemoglobin (gm/dl)	10.1	12.2	7.8-13.8 ± 1.65*
Total Erythrocyte Count (10 ⁶ /μl)	5.18	6.52	4.66-9.15 ± 1.42*
PCV (%)	36.1	35.5	38 ± 2.54*
MCV (fL)	69.7	69.0	47.8 ± 3.9 [#]
MCHC (gm%)	28.0	27.1	36.3 ± 2.1 [#]
MCH (pg)	19.5	18.7	17.3 ± 2.04 [#]
Total leucocyte count (10 ³ /μl)	26.4	11.06	6.2-11.05 ± 4.21*
Neutrophil (%)	78	65	57-75 ± 5.08*
Lymphocyte (%)	16	28	18-35 ± 4.56*
Monocyte (%)	02	02	2-6 ± 1.21*
Eosinophil (%)	04	05	2-6 ± 1.3*
Basophils (%)	00	00	0-4 ± 1.21*
Platelet Count (10 ³ /μl)	292	324	259.45 ± 88 [#]
Biochemical Parameters			
Blood urea nitrogen (mg/dl)	71.9	34.9	6.5-48.2 ± 13.77*
Creatine (mg/dl)	2.19	2.3	1.6-4.6 ± 1.03*
Serum bilirubin (Total)mg%	1.09	1.0	-
Serum bilirubin (Direct)mg%	0.3	0.2	-
Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST) (IU/L)	135.0	15.0	14.4-84.0 ± 17.27*
Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) (IU/L)	141.0	29.0	21.2-109.0 ± 27.84*
Serum alkaline phosphate (IU/L)	44.00	81.0	-

Fig 3: X-rays of Tiger skull and hindlimb showing fractures in the skull and hind limb

Fig. 4: (a)Healing of wound in the forehead and at metatarsal region after 30 days.
(b)Healing status of wound after 30 days.